

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

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The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Member World Association Of Medical Editors*

"This journal is a member of and subscribes to the principles of the Committee on Publication Ethics".

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The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine: The indexation challenge

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The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine is one of the few Iraqi medical journals which have been indexed in more than one indexing systems including international indexing systems namely:

1-WHO index medicus:
EMR index medicus (EMR Virtual health science library).

2-EMR Journal information Directory
<http://www.emro.who.int/emrjorlist/default.aspx?lit=N>

3- EMR online Journals Directory
<http://www.emro.who.int/EMRJorList/Online.aspx>

4- EMR Union Catalogue for Health Sciences Journals:
<http://www.emro.who.int/HIS/unlist/default.asp>

5-Copernicus International Journal master list. <http://journals.indexcopernicus.com/>

6-EMR medex beta
<http://www.emrmedex.com/detail.asp>

We are pleased, to inform you that The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine is the only Iraqi Medical journal of the 105 online journals in EMR online Journals Directory available at <http://www.emro.who.int/EMRJorList/Online.aspx> [accessed at 14th of May 2008]

Journal indexing in international system is a great challenge for journals in developing countries. Our journal is now fully indexed and abstracted in Copernicus International journal master list at: <http://journals.indexcopernicus.com/karta.php>

Medical journals from many developing countries have been indexed in the US National Library of Medicine which is one of the most widely used journal index. Our journal has applied for this US index medicus indexation and the journal evaluation will be started once they receive 4 recent issues (Print copies).

There are no definite criteria for ensuring the acceptance of a journal in an indexing system and it is generally relied upon the decision of Literature Selection Technical Review Committee. One of our major goals is to become indexed in as many international indexing systems as possible.

Being indexed in Index Medicus which makes our abstracts retrievable from PubMed to a worldwide audience is especially one of our top priorities. One of the most important factors that ensure indexing is to publish the journal on time. This might seem a very simple task at first look; but actually, especially in our country, on time publication of a high quality journals a major task for the journal. This requires experienced, well-motivated and deadline oriented personnel. Having a clear and detailed work schedule also is very helpful in processing the manuscripts in the assembly line. An effective correspondence with the authors by e-mails would accelerate the process of editing manuscripts, especially those which undergo extensive editing and rewriting. We have previously partially fulfilled this aim as the print issue of April was release very early during the first week of the month. The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine is a general medical journal and its content should satisfy generalists and specially those who are outside the region but interested in the situation of health and medicine inside. Our international editorial board has already contributed to the achievement of this endeavor.

Another important factor is to have a reliable reviewing system which could verify the originality and validity of the submission to the editorial office. As our peer-reviewers do not exceed 50 in number, and we cannot exhaust them by sending too many manuscripts for review, we are largely relying on our international editorial board for evaluating the submitted manuscripts. Our evaluation includes statistical, methodological and bibliographical perspectives and verifies the originality, innovativeness and grammatical and compositional values of the article.

Hopefully this August issue will be the first to be submitted to the PubMed: The US national library of medicine.